

Paradigm of Common Property Resource Management for Sustainable Development

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Introduction

Resource in a narrow sense refers to something, which is useful and valuable and is meant to satisfy or helps to satisfy human needs. Every living being requires certain basic necessities that nature provides such as ideal environment, land, water, light, atmosphere, forest and biodiversity. The socio-economic development of man depends on the environment and this development influences the environment. Thus, environment and development are interdependent. Now-a-days "development" has become a comprehensive word carrying wide as well as specific meanings that both the common man and the specialist can use it in their own contexts. In fact, economic development is closely linked with the development of natural resources. These resources can be broadly classified into four categories, viz., i) private property resources ii) state property resources, iii) open access resources, and iv) common property resources.

In poor countries, common property resources make a valuable contribution to the sustainable livelihoods of rural populations. This includes the collection of fuel wood, fodder, crop wastes, cow dung, organic manure and other products that are derived from the bark, seeds, flowers and fruits of trees, as well as water for drinking, cooking, irrigation and local fisheries. The existence of imperfect factor markets results in an intimate link between the rural economy and its natural resources base. Inadequate rural employment opportunities, especially in the slack season, imply that the local commons can make substantial contributions to household incomes. Another important function of local common property resources is that they act as insurance against uncertainty in the absence of complete contingent markets. Access to such resources serves to prevent risks associated with natural disasters and crop failure. Furthermore, for landless populations, access to local common property resources may be the only available non-human asset.

The term “Common Property Resources” (CPRs) is broadly defined as natural resources in which a group of people has common user rights (not necessarily ownership rights). These include natural forests, community forests, community pastures, wastelands, common dumping places, threshing and winnowing grounds, watershed, drainage and village ponds, village lands, streams, rivers, groundwater and oceans. These may also include man-made resources like irrigation tanks, community wells and village roads.

Current Status of CPRs in India

In India, out of the total land area 328.73 million hectares, only about 159 million hectares are cultivated. The remaining 169.73 million hectares, consisting of forests, woodlands, grasslands, deserts, marshes, rivers lakes shorelines and other forms of common properties support many occupations like forestry and livestock rearing and provide daily requirements like food, fuel, fodder and medicines. According to NSSO (1999), the common property land resources forms 15 per cent to the total geographical area.

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is about enhancing human wellbeing through time. One should have the ability and opportunity to shape one’s life, which increase with better health, education and material comforts, enhancing the portfolio of assets. The World Commission on Environment and Development defined sustainable development as “progress that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own need. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition that sustainable development can only be achieved on the basis of a balanced appraisal of the environmental economic and social impacts of a country’s major development projects, as well as its development policies, plans and programmes.

Common property resources are currently valued primarily for their contributions to the rural economy, dominated by the output of goods (for subsistence, and increasingly for the market), contributions to rural employment, and the provision of local ecological services to farmers. There is a recognition of the role of such resources in maintaining catchments for urban water supplies, preserving biodiversity and for the risk – spreading functions, and increasingly for their potential role as carbon sinks, but these are currently underemphasized. With moderate growth, there is unlikely to be a substantial shift in the relative emphasis of these functions, although there may well be increasing pressures on common property resources as the scale of these demands increases with economic growth and population increase.

Need for Sustainable Development

Improving human wellbeing over time is a broader goal than increasing economic growth that focuses primarily on material comforts. This has some important implications. Since, social and environmental aspects also affects human wellbeing directly, a strict policy of ‘grow now, cleanup later’ involves costs for today’s generation, costs that often fall disproportionately on today’s poor. Durable economic growth is required for a serious attempt at poverty reduction. This means paying enough attention to social and environmental concerns so that durable growth is not affected (fig.1). There are limits to sustainability among assets, perhaps even more from the perspectives of peoples’ wellbeing. When environmental or natural assets are fairly abundant relative to human made assets, substitution of the former by the latter can be expected to lead to higher returns. Development strategy to date has often relied on drawing down environmental resources and replacing them with human made assets. Most developing countries’ growth strategy continues to

focus largely on the accumulation of human made assets (Physical Assets). The way an economy grows – pace and pattern of growth - can matter for the wellbeing of both the current generations’ children and grandchildren. Developing countries do not have to follow the path of development traversed in the industrial countries.

Sustainability perspective

The imperatives of economic efficiency, ecological health and socio-political democracy are interdependent. Sustainability is:

1. A normative standard or social goal; and
2. A vision of the future with many origin

There are at least two perspectives on sustainability, namely

1. The Ecological View: in this view, sustainability is premised on the integrity of the ecosystem because there is no human – made substitute.
2. The Social Science View: in this view, sustainability also requires democratic processes and a vital economy

Fig. 1: Sustainable Development

CPRs and Economic Securities

3.1. Income generative activities: Regular activities based on CPRs include the collection and sale of firewood, leaves made into plates and cups, fruits, grass for fodder, grass for thatching, honey and fish. Grass and tree fodder may also be fed to small ruminants, which can be a significant source of income, especially for the poor.

3.2. Direct inputs to Agriculture: Wood from forests is used in making agricultural implements and bullock carts and in fencing off fields. Forage from forests and non-forests land-based CPRs is needed to feed livestock, some of which are an integral part of the agricultural system. Drinking water for livestock is another pre-requisite for their maintenance that often comes from CPRs such as rivers, village ponds and tanks.

3.3. Direct inputs to the Home: Water and various fruits from CPRs are consumed by people, while firewood is essential for cooking food. Wood and grass for thatching are used in house construction and maintenance and wood is also used in furniture making.

3.4. A Safety Net for People During Drought Season: Since forest are relatively resilient in the

face of drought, many forest-based income-generative activities can continue when crop production has failed. In addition, some communities in forest areas fell trees in extreme drought years (but not in normal years) and sell the wood for firewood to generate income. Forests and other common lands may also be a source of emergency foods such as weeds, tubers and mammals.

CPRs and Security

4.1 Food Security: The role of CPRs in food production and filling the food gap in India has increased as a result of the management and the betterment of access to common property resources, particularly in irrigation channels. The bulk of the additional production of food grains, especially of marketable surplus, has come mainly from irrigated areas. There has, however, been some controversy with respect to the increase in agricultural production due to irrigation because of the complementary role of seeds, fertilizers, credit pricing and other factors. It is to say that a 'with' and 'without' methodology often used for estimating the contribution of irrigation to food production shows that yields per hectare have increased substantially due to irrigation. In addition, there are gains due to increasing area under cultivation, raising cropping intensity and improvement in cropping pattern, which were made possible due to rapid development in irrigation channels. Irrigation channels are also the catalyst for the use of other inputs. Development and better management of irrigation channels are, therefore, needed for attaining the objective of food security.

In addition to that, the CPRs ensure the food security of the rural poor. As mentioned above the poor purchasing power and the food security gap are fully covered by these resources. By availing of meat, milk and milk products of the live animals for their own consumption and for earning household income from the livestock animals, their food security is linked to their own productivity in which CPR utilisation pattern plays a critical role.

4.2. Livelihood Security: The three primary products of the bushland are crops, trees and grass. Those primary products are often combined with other inputs (e.g. labour, capital, livestock) to provide goods and services of value to people, including: (i) human food – meat and milk from domesticated livestock, bush meat, gathered foods and cereals (ii) energy – trees, tree products, manure, (iii) building materials – tree products, materials for thatching, materials for handicrafts; (iv) conservation of biological diversity, including the special cases in which local residents benefit from tourism and safari operations, and (v) sequestration of atmospheric carbon, especially in the roots of deep-rooted trees and grasses.

4.3. Empowerment: The poor who had significant and substantial stakes in the CPRs which were governed within the framework of the common property management, found that when they were given private land ownership, its productivity was declining. Jodha (1982, 1985, 1986, 1990 and 1996) also found that in the post-independence era, new markets opened for some of the CPR products resulting in over or unsustainable exploitation of the resources. His studies revealed that CPRs had contributed significantly towards employment and income of the poor where per household income ranged between Rs.530 and Rs.830 in different areas. Further, households earning less than Rs.4,800 per year were considered the poorest of the poor among those living below the poverty level income, which was Rs.6,400 per annum. Thus, the proportion of income from CPRs to total income ranged between 11 and 17 per cent in the case of the poorest household (Rs.4,800) and between 13 per cent in case of poor households (Rs.6,400).

4.4. Poverty Alleviation: As already discussed, the dependence of poorer household on CPRs is still a highly contested issue. It has been often argued that poor people extract more natural resources due to greater reliance on the natural resource base and also due to their high social discount rate. On the other hand, scholars posit that compared to the non-poor, the poor may depend more on the commons in relative terms, but in absolute terms their dependence is lower (Dasgupta, 1993), particularly for resources with good market opportunities. Consistent with growing theoretical literature on common-property resource management, there is a large quantum

of empirical research in India dealing with the dependence of the poor on the CPRs (Jodha, 1986, 1995; Beck and Ghosh, 2000). Beck and Nesmith (2001) noted that common property resources contribute about 12 per cent to the household income of poor rural households. In his study of common pool resources in West Bengal, India, Beck (1998) observes that access to CPR by the poor is gradually decreasing across all study villages and agro-ecological regions.

In their study of CPRs in different states of India, various authors find that CPRs contribute 1.1 per cent to 22.1 per cent, 10 per cent 27.3 per cent and 12 per cent of the income of poorer households in Gujarat, Karnataka, Punjab and West Bengal respectively, while this figure for non-poor/cultivating households was 0.1 to 11.4 per cent, 6.2 per cent, 22 per cent and 0.13 to 5.62 per cent in those states (Iyengar and Shukla, 1999, Singh etc., 1996, Beck and Ghosh, 2000). In a study of 29 Villages in South-Eastern Zimbabwe, Cavendish (1998, 1999) arrived at even larger estimates. He observes that the proportion of income based directly on the commons in about 35 per cent based on a qualitative assessment of babassu products in Maranho, Brazil, Hecht et al., (1988) also conclude that the products offer support to the poorest of the poor, especially the women.

Common Property Resources and Environment

5.1. Health: The World Health Organisation (WHO) estimates that 80 per cent of all incidence of sickness in developing countries can be traced to water and sanitation related causes. The prevention of infections of such an origin is one of the most important objectives of health and sanitation programmes in India. Human excreta should be disposed of in such a manner as to avoid direct or even indirect problems. According to Central Statistical Organization, in 2015, only 34 per cent of the rural population had access to sanitation services. In other words, 732 million people living in rural areas do not have access to toilets of any type. It is a fact that disease is a challenge to a developing country like India. The poor management of the common property resources such as public toilet, drainages and the drinking water are causes for disease in the rural areas. Better management of these resources will give a pollution free and diseases free environment to the nation.

5.2. Environmental services: Forests act as a sponge when it rains, regulating water flows, preventing flash floods and prolonging the period during which surface water is available. Where forests are on hillocks near to farmers' fields they also prevent stones and poor quality soil being washed off the hillock and deposited in farmers' fields while supplying nutrients to the fields in the form of leaf litter.

Conclusion

While the CPR has a unique role in providing food and food security, it shares this role with several other sectors in providing income and livelihood security. And yet, it is the income generating power of the CPR which is most important for poverty alleviation since it helps in the attainment of both CPR and food security and enables them to be self-sustaining over a long period without any resort to subsidy. Breakthroughs in productivity and income in poverty concentration areas can take place by creating CPRs. Water reservoirs of all types and sizes, watershed management recharging underground water storage etc., should be taken up with renewed vigor but without losing sight of the environment and the human aspects. Technologies and institutions appropriate to small farmers may receive special encouragement. Development of power will be needed for exploiting the ground water potential and the operation of grain storage facilities, especially the regurgitated ones. Drainage schemes may be fed into irrigation schemes to maintain favorable self-balance in the soil. At the same time, output from permanent CPRs like tanks, ponds, with respect to fishery and agriculture products like Makhana and Sinhara in India should be raised by appropriate methods including regular desilting and deepening. These measures taken along with those for strengthening institutions of marketing, credit and grain storage will boost agricultural production and sustainable development in poor areas.